

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-262-YANS-OJH-1% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230303
Vial:	107	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 262
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	250.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 250.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/3/2023 3:57:21 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 10:13:42 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.183	291445	49.76	12450
2	12.203	294228	50.24	12754

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-276-YANS-OJH-1% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230303
Vial:	108	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 276
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	250.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 250.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/3/2023 4:13:02 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 10:14:53 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.272	63127	3.09	2443
2	12.289	1980977	96.91	82615